

SHORT COMMUNICATIONS

Iron (III)-2-Hydroxy-3-Naphthoic Acid Chelate

S. L. Gupta and R. N. Soni

In our earlier paper¹, we have reported the composition and instability constant of the complex formed by the interaction of iron(III) and 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid in aqueous medium. This study has now been extended for the determination of instability constants at various ionic strengths and at different temperatures. The molecular extinction coefficient of the complex was found to be 2.30×10^3 . The instability constant of the complex—

$$K_{in} = \frac{\{[Fe^{3+}]_{Total} - [Complex]\}\{[acid]_{Total} - [complex]\}}{[Complex]}$$

has been calculated at various ionic strengths and are reported in Table I.

TABLE I

Effect of ionic strength on instability constant of the complex between Fe^{+3} ion and 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid in aqueous medium

$$\lambda = 570 \text{ m}\mu; \text{ pH} = 2.6; \text{ Temp.} = 30^\circ \pm 0.1.$$

Ionic strength	Instability constant
0.02	1.04×10^{-5}
0.05	1.08×10^{-5}
0.08	1.17×10^{-5}
0.10	1.36×10^{-5}
0.15	1.48×10^{-5}
0.20	1.67×10^{-5}

The instability constant of the complex has also been obtained at different temperatures. The results are recorded in Table II. The logarithm of the instability constants have been plotted against $1/T$ and from the slope of the straight line thus obtained, ΔH has been found to be -4.09 k.cal/mole. Assuming this to be constant over the range of experi-

mental temperatures, the value of ΔS has been calculated as 35.5 e.u. The probable structure of the complex may be assigned as

TABLE II

Instability constant of the complex at different temperatures

Ionic strength = 0.02; $\lambda = 570 \text{ m}\mu$; pH = 2.6

Temp. °K	Instability constant
283.16	1.43×10^{-5}
293.16	1.25×10^{-5}
303.16	1.04×10^{-5}
313.16	8.45×10^{-6}
323.16	6.87×10^{-6}
333.16	5.61×10^{-6}

Department of Chemistry,
Birla Institute of Technology and Science,
Pilani (Rajasthan), India.

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